

HYBRID RICE

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Performance of hybrid rice Wei-You 64 in international yield trials

Hybrid rice Wei-You 64, developed through collaboration between Chinese and IRRI scientists, was tested under irrigated conditions in the 1986 International Rice Yield Nursery of very early maturity (IRYN-VE). Data from 22 locations (4 each in Bangladesh, China, India, and Thailand; 3 in Pakistan; and one each in Egypt, Philippines, and Turkey) indicated that the hybrid produced the highest yield at 8 locations where the yield increase over the best inbreds in the trial ranged from 0.2 to 1.8 t/ha. The yields at different locations ranged from 1.5 t/ha in Phan

(Thailand) to 10.3 t/ha in Sakha (Egypt), reports Dr. D. V. Seshu, head of the International Rice Testing Program at IRRI. Its performance has been particularly good at four locations in China, where the yields ranged from 7.1 to 7.9 t/ha. The relatively poor performance at 14 of the 22 locations outside China suggests that hybrids developed in one country may have limited adaptability in other countries. There is, therefore, a need to develop region-specific heterotic hybrids using locally adapted parental lines.

Wei-You 64 hybrid.

New elite restorer lines identified at IRRI

IRRI's hybrid rice breeding program identified 73 new restorer lines for the WA cytotesterility system during 1987. Some of the restorers are among released varieties and elite lines developed at IRRI (viz., IR66 R, IR28228-12-3-1-1-2 R, IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 R, IR32429-68-3-3-3 R, IR32809-26-3-3 R, IR35366-28-3-1-2-2 R, IR35366-62-1-2-2-3 R, IR37721-9-2-1-3 R, and IR39357-133-3-2-2-2 R and national rice improvement programs of the Philippines (C1321-90 R, MRC1105-430 R), Malaysia (Mahsuri R), Pakistan (PDR 76-D10-D8-D R), Korea (Iri 378 R, Suweon 347 R, and Milyang 83 R) and Colombia (5167 R). The suffix R indicates that these lines are purified for restorer genes. Seeds of these lines are available from IRRI for use in national hybrid rice breeding programs.

Promising F₁ rice hybrids for Korea

During the past 5 years, Korean rice scientists evaluated in replicated yield trials at various locations in Korea several experimental rice hybrids, developed collaboratively with IRRI. Hybrid V20 A/Milyang 46 R showed 16% (1.2 t/ha) higher yield than the inbred check varieties (see table). However, its grain quality inherited from the female parent from China is not acceptable in Korea.

IRRI and Korean scientists have, therefore, been working to develop